

Nature-based Solutions Typologies and Ecological Processes

About this brief

This brief presents a comprehensive outline of 1) the **NbS typologies** of generic and specific **actions** that can be done to reduce vulnerability to negative impacts on an ecosystem and 2) the **ecological processes** underpinning NbS interventions across **six distinct landscape-thematic areas**:

- ▶ Freshwater management
- ▶ Agriculture
- ▶ Urban areas
- ▶ Mountain areas
- ▶ Coastal areas
- ▶ Forested areas

For more details and sources, read Chapter and 4 of the Invest4Nature report:

[Value categories and approaches to assess NBS economic and financial performance \(Deliverable 2.1\)](#)

➤ [Read the full report](#)

Context

Today, nature-based solutions (NbS) are widely recognised in scientific and policy domains for **addressing societal challenges**. This follows the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) definition: *“actions to protect, sustainably manage and restore natural or modified ecosystems that address societal challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits”*.

However, a significant gap exists in our understanding of the economic implications of NbS, which is crucial for informed resource allocation and financing decisions by policymakers and practitioners.

To bridge a part of this knowledge gap, Invest4Nature has compiled a report providing a **comprehensive exploration of NbS typologies** across six distinct landscape types and thematic areas, along with a list of valuation methods. It looks at the costs and benefits of NBS and different ways to measure the various values people attribute to NBS benefits. This work offers valuable insight to practitioners and others seeking to have a better understanding of NbS and their economic implications.

Source:
Network Nature

In Invest4Nature's study, **societal challenges** are defined as:

- ▶ Climate change adaptation (flooding, heat, storms, drought),
- ▶ Climate change mitigation (GHG emissions),
- ▶ Natural hazards (avalanches, landslides),
- ▶ Environmental management (pollution of air and water, noise pollution, water scarcity, erosion, and biodiversity loss),
- ▶ Socio-economic challenges (unemployment, inequality, health & wellbeing, social segregation and economic efficiency).
- ▶ Sustainable management approaches developing multi-functional ecosystems and landscapes, with improved ecosystem

NbS actions are divided into three **generic categories** associated with different types of ecosystem interventions:

- ▶ **Type 1** – minimal or no intervention in ecosystems, aimed at preserving or enhancing ecosystem services
- ▶ **Type 2** – sustainable management approaches developing multi-functional ecosystems and landscapes, with improved ecosystem services
- ▶ **Type 3** - managing ecosystems in very intrusive ways or even creating new ecosystems

Each generic NbS action can be further divided into **specific NbS actions** generating multiple environmental, socio-cultural and economic benefits simultaneously.

In this work, NbS actions have been defined across six different types of landscapes and land uses: Coastal areas; Mountain areas; Freshwater, Forests, Agriculture; and Urban areas.

Freshwater Management

Water management is severely affected by climate change. Altered precipitation patterns, increasing both intensity and frequency lead to more extreme rainfall, floods, and droughts. These changes impact freshwater ecosystems, influencing water quality and availability.

Source:
Network Nature

Challenge: Flood

One of the main challenges that NbS in water management can help address is river and pluvial flooding. Heavy rainfall can cause water flow to exceed river capacity, leading to overflow, while in urban areas with extensive impervious surfaces, excessive rainwater can overwhelm drainage systems.

NbS help mitigate floods by absorbing excess water, reducing runoff, and preserving river structure through sediment transport. Water-sensitive planning and design can further minimize runoff, decrease flood peaks, and improve groundwater recharge.

NbS Typologies

NbS Type – Generic Action	Specific Action
1 – Protection of hydrology and of existing groundwater resources	Maintenance of safe physical environments to promote hydrogeological stability
2 – Modification of an existing hydrological ecosystem	Rehabilitation and restoration of rivers, floodplains, basins, wetlands, ponds, lakes and aquifers
	Water-sensitive forest management
	Groundwater restoration and management
3 – Creation of new water-related ecosystems	Rainwater harvesting
	Phytoremediation
	Urban green space and corridors

These actions contribute to regulate floods and droughts, maintain water balance, increase storage capacity, and prevent saltwater intrusion.

NbS and Ecological Processes for Flood Risk Reduction:

Floodplain restoration

Floodplains act as natural buffers, slowing water movement, enhancing groundwater absorption, and reducing flood risks to people and infrastructure.

- ▶ Maintaining hydrological connectivity strengthens their ability to retain excess water, reduce peak flows, and minimize downstream damage.
- ▶ Allowing space for natural river and floodplain dynamics lowers flood exposure while creating essential water pathways.

River restoration, including floodplain restoration, re-meandering and water retention measures, showed positive effects on flood protection in several studies.

Urban water retention measures

Urban water retention measures, such as bioswales and retention and detention basins, enhance permeable surface areas through vegetation.

- ▶ By improving soil permeability, they facilitate water infiltration, reduce surface runoff, and increase groundwater storage, helping to mitigate flood risks during heavy rainfall events.

Bioretention systems, such as ponds, swales and rain gardens, are effective in peak discharge control, with an average reduction above 40%

Agriculture

Agriculture is a sector regularly threatened by climate hazards. Heat stress can cause crop and livestock loss, increase the risk of pests and disease outbreaks, and exacerbate the water scarcity of droughts. In addition, flooding can cause damage to crop yields, transport and infrastructure.

Source: Network Nature

Challenge: Drought

Droughts occur due to prolonged reductions in precipitation, often lasting a season or more. Their onset is influenced by factors such as temperature fluctuations, strong winds, low humidity, and rainfall patterns, including the distribution, intensity, and duration of rain events during crop-growing season.

Natural processes that enhance water infiltration, evapotranspiration, and rainwater storage help maintain water availability, improve quality, and reduce risks associated with droughts and other water-related disasters.

NbS Typologies

NbS Type – Generic Action	Specific Action
1 – Protection of agricultural ecosystems	Protection of trees in forests and wetlands
	Protection of trees in forests and wetlands
	Conservation agriculture
2 – Modification of an existing agricultural ecosystem management	Paludiculture (including peatland and wetland restoration)
	No or minimum tillage
	Crop type diversification and rotation
	Mulching and use of cover crops
3 – Creation of new agricultural ecosystems	Agroforestry
	Mixed crop-livestock systems
	Creation of micro-relief, and construction of floodplains for rainwater harvesting

These actions contribute to sustain crop yields, improve soil and water management, support biodiversity, pollination, and pest control while conserving moisture and maintaining productivity, nutrient cycling and soil fertility.

NbS and Ecological Processes for Drought:

Vegetated buffer zones

Vegetated buffer areas help mitigate drought and water scarcity by retaining and gradually releasing runoff, enhancing groundwater recharge, and maintaining minimum ecological river flows.

- ▶ Through water filtration, vegetation and soil help reduce soil erosion and water pollution.

Buffer areas and filter strips can reduce water overflow up to 50% on average.

Agroforestry & sustainable agricultural practices

Cover crops enhances water infiltration rates and soil moisture levels. They promote balanced evapotranspiration and mitigate the effects of extreme weather conditions.

- ▶ Acting as an insulating layer, they lower surface soil temperature and mitigate wind effects, reducing soil water evaporation.
- ▶ By mitigating hot wind impact, excessive crop transpiration and water uptake are minimized, preserving soil moisture reserves.

Wooded vegetation significantly decreases wind speed, reducing crop transpiration rates and unnecessary soil water loss.

- ▶ It improves soil quality by augmenting soil organic matter and mitigating erosion.

Mulching contributes to increased water infiltration rates and soil moisture retention in agricultural soil, thereby

Bioretention systems, such as ponds, swales and rain gardens, are effective in peak discharge control, with an average reduction above 40%

Urban Areas

Urban ecosystems are natural systems within cities or densely populated areas. Climate change and environmental challenges increase the risk of flooding, heat stress, pollution and health concerns.

Source: Network Nature

Challenge: Heat stress

Urban heat islands and heat stress occur in cities where natural green cover is replaced by concrete pavements, buildings and heat-absorbing surfaces. For urban populations, these effects contribute to increased energy costs for cooling and heat-related health problems.

Vegetation plays a critical role in influencing urban microclimates by providing shading and evapotranspiration services that help reduce and regulate surface and atmospheric temperatures.

NbS Typologies

NbS Type – Generic Action	Specific Action
1 – Protection of high-quality urban ecosystems	Protection of urban trees, forests, green spaces and parks
	Protection of blue infrastructure: wetlands, lakes, streams, riverbanks
2 – Modification of urban ecosystems	Rehabilitation and restoration of urban habitats, green space and corridors
	Rehabilitation and restoration of blue infrastructure
	Reforestation of urban and peri-urban forests
3 – Creation of new urban ecosystems	Creation of urban parks, forest, street trees, vegetable gardens and greening the building (green roofs, green facades, vertical greening system)
	Creation of retention ponds, temporary water storage, infiltration basins, filter strips, SUDS, day-lighting of streams

These actions contribute to reduce the urban heat island effect, capture CO₂, and improve water infiltration, support biodiversity, improve human well-being and provide economic benefits.

NbS and Ecological Processes for Heat stress:

Urban vegetation

Plant leaves absorb solar energy for photosynthesis or reflect it back into the atmosphere, cooling the area below. Simultaneously, water drawn up by the roots is released through the leaves and evaporates, using heat from the surrounding air.

- ▶ By lowering energy demand, vegetation indirectly reduces greenhouse gas emissions, helping to mitigate climate change

Trees significantly reduce urban temperatures, with surface temperatures in tree-covered areas being 0-4 °C lower in Southern Europe and 8-12 °C lower in Central Europe compared to urban areas without vegetation.

Green roofs & walls

Vegetation on rooftops and walls provides thermal insulation by blocking sunlight and reducing heat transmission into buildings.

- ▶ Green roofs minimize heat emissions and create an insulating air layer.
- ▶ Green walls enhance shading effects, cooling adjacent buildings and paved surfaces.
- ▶ Both systems contribute to energy savings through insulation and evapotranspiration.

In the Mediterranean climate, green buildings could reduce energy demand for air conditioning by 40-60%.

Mountain Areas

Mountain areas are particularly susceptible to climate change impacts, including reduced precipitation and rising temperatures at higher elevations. These changes heighten the risk of rockslides, snow avalanches, flooding, and water shortages.

Source: Canva

Challenge: Landslides & Avalanches

Avalanches and landslides involve the downward movement of snow, rocks, or soil on sloped terrain.

Protecting and restoring forests can help mitigate these risks by helping to stabilise the ground, reducing the likelihood of mass movements and incrementing water infiltration. Vegetation can also effectively reinforce shallow soils and surface layers against landslides and slowdown water reducing flood risk. In addition, terracing of steep slope and green flood barriers can reduce soil erosion, sediment deposition and nutrients

NbS Typologies

NbS Type – Generic Action	Specific Action
1 – Protection of mountain ecosystems	Maintenance of protection forests (a forest that can prevent a recognized potential damage due to an existing natural hazard or reduce the associated risks)
2 – Modification of mountain ecosystems	Terracing with drainage/ Slope stabilization /Revegetation of steep slopes
	Reforestation and/or revegetation of mountain areas
3 – Creation of new mountain ecosystems	Afforestation of mountain areas
	Green flood barriers

These actions contribute to reduce soil erosion, rockfalls, landslides, debris flows and snow avalanches, while increase water retention.

NbS and Ecological Processes for Storm and Coastal Erosion:

Avalanches mitigation

- ▶ Standing and fallen trees contribute to snowpack stability, helping to prevent avalanches or limit their magnitude.
- ▶ In forests, the presence of trees and vegetation canopy influences snowfall distribution and modifies the energy exchange at the snow surface. In addition, it can act as natural barrier slowing down small-scale avalanches

These localized variations in the snowpack, can reduce the likelihood of weak layers that could trigger avalanches.

Forest type affects avalanche dynamics differently. Evergreen coniferous and mixed forests have a greater stabilizing effect than deciduous coniferous forests due to their higher crown biomass, interception capacity, and denser small-diameter stems

Landslides mitigation

For landslides mitigation, trees and shrubs with deep roots play a pivotal role.

- ▶ In shallow soils, roots penetrate the full depth, anchoring into more stable layers.
- ▶ Dense lateral roots reinforce soil surface layers, reducing landslide risks.
- ▶ Forests act as natural barriers, slowing and blocking small debris flows and rockfalls.

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Coastal Areas

Coastal regions face multiple hazards, including extreme storm surges, rising sea levels, droughts, heat waves, landslides, and ocean acidification. These threats contribute to land loss, coastal erosion, flooding, and saltwater intrusion, making these areas highly vulnerable to climate change and environmental degradation.

Challenge: Storm & Coastal Erosion

Coastal areas are highly vulnerable to extreme weather events such as storms, which bring strong winds, heavy rainfall, and high wave energy. These events can lead to storm surges, flooding, and erosion.

Rising sea levels, intensified by climate change, exacerbate coastal erosion, removing rocks, soil, and sand.

NbS can help increase resilience. Coastal vegetation, mangrove forests, barrier islands, coral reefs, and dunes act as natural defenses against wind and waves. Additionally, planting vegetation or adding sediment stabilizes the coastline and enhances its ability to absorb and dissipate storm energy, mitigating the impacts of coastal flooding and erosion.

NbS Typologies

NbS Type – Generic Action	Specific Action
1 – Protection/conservation of coastal ecosystems	Protection of barrier islands, sea grasses (seafloor vegetation), salt marshes, coral & oyster reefs, and coastal vegetation
2 – Modification of coastal ecosystems	Managed realignment of coastal areas
	Restoration of coastal habitats in transitional waters, e.g., dunes, seagrasses, wetlands, saltmarshes, oyster & reef species
3 – Creation of new coastal ecosystems	Near-shore enhancement of coastal morphology, e.g., restoration of barrier islands, beach nourishment, dune reconstruction, cliff stabilisation
	Engineered hybrid solutions: Natural solutions combined with built structures, such as, green dikes, wooded fences and vegetated levees, which are combined with structural dykes

These actions contribute to limit erosion, dissipate wave energy, improve biodiversity, enhance carbon sequestration, maintain habitats essential to secure aquatic biomass and hence food supply.

NbS and Ecological Processes for Storm & Coastal Erosion:

Mangrove forest

Mangrove forests and wetlands help reduce wave energy and slow down water flow over soil surfaces. The decrease in water speed lowers its ability to displace and transport sediments, promoting sediment deposition in these areas.

- ▶ These ecosystems contribute to stabilizing coastal regions by increasing sediment accumulation, which can enhance resilience to erosion and flooding.

Coastal vegetation and mangroves contribute also to create and preserve unique habitat for flora and fauna

Vegetated dunes

Vegetation like dune grass helps stabilize the shoreline, with root systems anchoring plants and stabilizing soil.

- ▶ Tree roots create intricate networks underground, stabilizing sediment and reducing erosion by holding onto soil particles and absorbing water, which increases the soil's strength.

In the Mediterranean climate, green buildings could reduce energy demand for air conditioning by 40-60%.

Forested Areas

Forests play a key role in climate change mitigation and adaptation. Their protection and restoration help regulate water flow, control pests and diseases, and stabilize slopes, thus contributing to biodiversity. Forests mitigate flood impacts through water absorption, sequester carbon to reduce climate change, and alleviate heat waves by providing shade and cooling the environment via transpiration.

Source: Network Nature

Challenge: Carbon emissions

Terrestrial ecosystems play a crucial role in the carbon cycle, contributing to store carbon and mitigate climate change. Terrestrial carbon includes organic and inorganic carbon stored in soils and vegetation, encompassing both living and dead biomass. Terrestrial ecosystems absorb and retain atmospheric carbon, helping mitigate rising CO₂ levels.

NbS can help mitigating climate change impacts, in particular, forests hold substantial carbon in above- and below-ground biomass. Shrublands and grasslands also contribute by capturing CO₂ through photosynthesis and storing carbon in plant tissues and soil.

NbS typologies

NbS Type –Generic Action	Specific Action
1 – Protection/conservation of forest ecosystems	Protection/conservation of primary and old-growth forests
2 – Modification of an existing forest ecosystem / Sustainable forest management	Restoration of degraded forests
	Maintenance of forests in riparian buffers and headwater areas
	Reforestation / revegetation (e.g., regrowth of deciduous trees to reduce risks of future diebacks)
3 – Creation of new forest ecosystems	Afforestation
	Integrating trees and forests into other landscapes (e.g., urban areas) or sectors (e.g., agroforestry)

These actions contribute to enhance water flow regulation, trap sediments and pollutants from other land use activities, improve habitat quality and diversity, enhance landscape connectivity, mitigate water scarcity, absorbing CO₂ and mitigate temperatures.

NbS and ecological processes for carbon sequestration

Forests function as carbon sink:

- ▶ Forests absorb CO₂ through photosynthesis, converting it into glucose, oxygen, and plant biomass.
- ▶ The captured carbon is stored in living vegetation, dead wood, leaf litter, and forest soils, contributing to long-term carbon sequestration

Global forests are net carbon sinks of -7.6 ± 49 Gt CO₂eq /year, accounting for gross carbon removals

- ▶ Carbon fluxes are largely dependent on the type of vegetation, on the geographical location of the forest and on some hydrological aspects – such as the depth of unsaturated zones.

Avoided deforestation and land degradation increases carbon storage by up to 0.4-5.8 Gt CO₂eq per year

